

Arbuscular mycorrhizal status of *Atriplex* (Chenopodioideae: Amaranthaceae) with some observations of fungal endophytes in roots of *Atriplex amnicola*, *A. cinerea* and *A. nummularia* grown as exotics in a Central Anatolian soil

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Abstract. The chenopod genus *Atriplex* (saltbushes) contains many environmentally and economically important species that grow in harsh environments where it is likely that root endophytic fungi contribute to their ecological success. Despite the Chenopodioideae being considered to predominantly contain non-mycorrhizal species, there are many reports of arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF) in *Atriplex* roots but mostly without arbuscules being observed or their functionality determined. This study undertook the first systematic collation of this information (28 reports). Also, observations are included on fungal endophyte colonisation of *Atriplex amnicola*, *A. cinerea* and *A. nummularia* cultured as exotics in a Central Anatolian soil. With about 10% of all *Atriplex* spp. examined for AMF, 22 species are reported as mycorrhizal, nine with arbuscules (mostly at a low incidence) and clear growth benefits only in *A. nummularia* (2 reports), leaving open to doubt the universal functionality of these associations. Although, AMF associations in these species were not detected in that context, DSE and a possible actinobacterial endophyte were found. This work highlights the need for more work on AMF and other root endophytes in *Atriplex* across a wider range of conditions, and especially the need to demonstrate the functionality (if any) of these, possibly rudimentary, associations.

Keywords: Actinobacteria, arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi, *Atriplex*, dark septate endophytes, root endophytes, saltbushes

Released online 4 March 2026

Introduction

In the subfamily Chenopodioideae (F. Amaranthaceae), species of *Atriplex* (saltbushes) are the most widely reported to form associations with arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF), but this information has not been collated or examined systematically, nor has the functionality of these associations been fully investigated. With some 260 species of *Atriplex* (Başköse and Yaprak, 2019), these are important components of many ecosystems as well as a diverse resource for agricultural

production, agroecosystem use and ecological restoration, especially in contexts with soil constraints (salinity, alkalinity and low fertility) and periods of aridity. Thirty years ago, Le Houérou (1992) reviewed the potential of *Atriplex* spp. as agroecosystem plants in the Mediterranean Basin and such analyses could be profitably undertaken for other major agricultural regions for both endemic and exotic species. At the time of Le Houérou's review, it was understood that *Atriplex* and other chenopods were non-mycorrhizal or only

incidentally colonised when growing in association with neighbouring mycorrhizal species (Hirrel *et al.*, 1978). With increasing numbers of *Atriplex* spp. reported to form associations with AMF, it is important that a possible change in understanding of *Atriplex* be recognised and considered when evaluating agricultural and agroecosystem use of members of this genus. This consideration should also motivate further investigation of AMF in additional species and contexts, given that it is likely that AMF contribute to the tolerance of members of the genus to problematic soils, such as in Central Anatolia, Turkey (see Riley, 2021 for some contextual background).

In addition to AMF, other kinds of endophytic fungi have been recorded in the roots of *Atriplex* (e.g., Barrow *et al.*, 1997). In particular, non-pathogenic fungi described as dark septate endophytes (DSE), which are considered common across a wide range of plants, have been recorded but their potential mutualism has not been fully elucidated (Jumpponen and Trappe, 1998; Mandyam and Jumpponen, 2005). Apart from the work of Barrow and colleagues, and Cofré *et al.* (2012), DSE have not otherwise been reported in *Atriplex*.

In Turkey, there are some 20 species of *Atriplex* (Başköse and Yaprak, 2019), so these represent an important component of its flora. However, limited consideration has been given to either native or exotic *Atriplex* spp. for agroecosystem potential in Turkey. Some examples are work on erosion control (Şahin and Özcan, 2020) and the fodder value (Erdoğan *et al.*, 2013) of *Atriplex canescens* (introduced from the USA), and an unpublished study assessing various plants including *Atriplex hortensis* (a Eurasian native) for arid-zone revegetation (Oktay Yildiz, 2016). Not unexpectedly, there have been no investigations of root endophyte colonisation of *Atriplex* spp. growing in Turkish soil. Within the Mediterranean Basin, there are only two AMF records for *Atriplex* spp.: *Atriplex halimus*, an ecologically important and versatile species native to the region (Walker *et al.*, 2014), in the Negev Highlands, Israel (He *et al.*, 2002) and Oran, Algeria (Sidhoum and Fortas, 2018); and *A. canescens*, an introduced species (Sidhoum and Fortas, 2018).

The purpose of this work was (1) to collate published information on the status of *Atriplex* as hosts of AMF or other root endophytes, and (2) to make preliminary observations on possible fungal endophyte colonisation of *Atriplex amnicola*, *A. cinerea* and *A. nummularia* (Australian natives used for various agroecosystem purposes) roots in a representative Central Anatolian soil in Niğde, Turkey. The latter might confirm the AMF status of *A. nummularia* in a new soil context and indicate the

potential of *A. amnicola* and *A. cinerea* as AMF hosts. This species choice was based solely on availability of material, but nevertheless, could provide useful new information. Knowing the likelihood of *Atriplex* spp. to form beneficial root endophyte associations in a soil from a degraded context in Central Anatolia might encourage their future assessment for revegetation purposes in the region.

Materials and methods

Overview of AMF in *Atriplex*

Literature indexed or discoverable through online biographic databases (Web of Science, Clarivate, London, UK; Google Scholar, Google, Mountain View, CA, USA; Scopus, Elsevier, Amsterdam, Netherlands), and through citations within primary research papers and relevant reviews were included if observational or experimental work on *Atriplex* AMF was reported. Zotero (zotero.org) was used for reference management. Various data were collected and summarised from these reports as detailed in Table 1.

Seed and field soil sources

Single accessions of *Atriplex amnicola*, *A. cinerea* and *A. nummularia* (Anu2) were obtained from a commercial seed supplier (Seed Shed, Donnybrook, WA, Australia) and an additional accession of *A. nummularia* (Anu1) was collected from plants growing alongside Purnong Road, Mannum, South Australia, Australia (34°52'3.2" S, 139°22'36.8" E; 3 July 2019). Seeds of *A. nummularia* (Anu1) and *A. cinerea* had to be removed from their enclosing bracteoles before use. The other two accessions were supplied as cleaned seed. Top soil was collected from a recently cultivated field that had been under weedy fallow for many years (37°56'17.5" N, 34°37'34.4" E; see Riley *et al.*, 2021 for soil analysis details).

Plant growth

Seed was germinated in a perlite-peat mixture (50:50) in a growth chamber (23-25°C, 45-50% RH) in pots covered with plastic bags until emergence. When the seedlings were about 30 mm long, these pots were transferred to the greenhouse (c. 25°C) for the plants to acclimatise for about 3 weeks before transplanting single plants to local field soil in square plastic pots (100 x 100 x 170 mm, 900 ml, 5 pots per accession, 11 August 2020). These pots were placed on a greenhouse bench in a completely randomised layout and bottom watered until harvested. No fertiliser was added. Three

Table 1. Published records of arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF) associated with *Atriplex* spp. (Amaranthaceae)

Natv, native species in the study region (logical); Fld, field study (logical); Inoc, inoculum applied (logical); \bar{x} , values given are means of treatment stratum not the full data set (logical); n, number (actual or best estimate) of observational/experimental units examined (excluding uninoculated units in sterilised substrates or those unlikely to contain AMF propagules); F%, frequency of AMF positive experimental units; M%, percentage of mycorrhizal colonisation (hypha, vesicle and/or arbuscule presence); V%, percentage of vesicle presence; A%, percentage of arbuscule presence; percentages of AMF structure presence were determined by proportion of colonised root fragments or microscope fields depending on the study, where proportion is not reported then only presence ("present") or absence (0) is given; logicals are 1 for yes and 0 for no; a dash indicates information that is not reported; †, annual species; and DSE, dark septate endophytic fungi.

Source	Province/State/Region	Species	Natv	Fld	Inoc	\bar{x}	n	F%	M%	V%	A%	Observational units and other notes
Bevege, 1968	unspecified, Australia	<i>A. vesicaria</i>	1	1	0	na	-	-	present	-	-	no details provided
Williams <i>et al.</i> , 1974; Williams and Aldon, 1976	New Mexico, USA	<i>A. canescens</i>	1	1	0	na	4	-	present	present	?present	soil sample with roots traced from host; unclear if arbuscules were observed in <i>A. canescens</i>
Hirrel <i>et al.</i> , 1978	Illinois, USA	<i>A. hortensis</i> †	0	0	1	na	8	0	0	-	-	plant in pots of autoclaved soil
		<i>A. canescens</i>	1	1	0	na	3	0	0	-	-	plant grown adjacent to citrus trees in the field
		<i>A. confertifolia</i>	1	1	0	na	-	-	present	-	-	single plant; AMF only on undisturbed sites; colonisation common
Miller, 1979	Wyoming, USA	<i>A. gardneri</i>	1	1	0	0	-	0-35	present	-	-	single plant; AMF only on undisturbed sites; colonisation less common than other hosts
		<i>A. patula</i> †	0	1	0	na	-	-	0	-	-	single plant; annual host only on disturbed sites
		<i>A. rosea</i> †	0	1	0	na	-	-	0	-	-	single plant; annual host only on disturbed sites
Allen, 1983	Wyoming, USA	<i>A. gardneri</i>	1	1	0	0	9	-	3-78	0-present	0-25	root system of host; seasonally variable
Miller <i>et al.</i> , 1983	Wyoming, USA	<i>A. confertifolia</i>	1	1	0	0	~30	0-present	0-80	-	-	root sample traced to host; mostly in association with other host plant
Bethlenfalvay <i>et al.</i> , 1984	California, USA	<i>A. gardneri</i>	1	1	0	0	-	0	0	-	-	root sample traced to host
		<i>A. polycarpa</i>	1	1	0	0	1	-	>50%	-	-	root sample from isolated plant
Tester, 1993	South Australia, Australia	<i>A. vesicaria</i>	1	0	0	na	-	-	4-20	present	0	root sample
Sigüenza <i>et al.</i> , 1996	California, USA	<i>A. julacea</i>	1	1	0	0	50	0-present	0-48	0-30	0-17	pot; 0% alone, 14-45% with companion plant (onion) with AMF
Barrow <i>et al.</i> , 1997	New Mexico and Colorado, USA	<i>A. canescens</i>	1	1	0	1	160	-	9-69	0-present	0	soil sample with roots from under host; seasonally variable
	Tarapacá and Antofagasta, Chile	<i>A. atacamensis</i>	1	1	0	1	15	-	45	-	-	root sample from host; seasonally and geographically variable, DSE present
	Coquimbo, Chile	<i>A. coquimbensis</i>	1	1	0	1	5	-	1	-	-	

Table 1. Published records of arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF) associated with *Atriplex* spp. (Amaranthaceae) (continued)

Source	Province/State/Region	Species	Natv	Fld	Inoc	\bar{x}	n	F%	M%	V%	A%	Observational units and other notes
	Atacama and Coquimbo, Chile	<i>A. deserticola</i>	1	1	0	1	10	-	47	-	-	
	Atacama, Chile	<i>A. madariagae</i>	1	1	0	1	5	-	21	-	-	
Aguilera <i>et al.</i> , 1998	Antofagasta, Chile	<i>A. microphylla</i>	1	1	0	1	5	-	25	-	-	soil sample from under host
	Atacama, Chile	<i>A. mucronata</i>	1	1	0	1	5	-	12	-	-	
	Coquimbo, Chile	<i>A. nummularia</i>	0	1	0	1	10	-	31	-	-	
	Coquimbo, Chile	as <i>A. podocarpa</i> , a synonym of <i>A. deserticola</i>	1	1	0	1	5	-	0	-	-	single host pot; <i>Melilotus officinalis</i> in the same experiment formed AMF associations
	Coquimbo, Chile	<i>A. repanda</i>	1	1	0	1	45	-	5	-	-	
Wanek <i>et al.</i> , 1999	Wyoming, USA	<i>A. canescens</i>	1	0	0/1	0	45	0	0	-	-	soil core, varied with soil depth
He <i>et al.</i> , 2002	Negev Highlands, Israel	<i>A. halimus</i>	1	1	0	1	4	-	21-29	12-20	1-4	soil core, varied with soil depth
Asghari <i>et al.</i> , 2005	South Australia, Australia	<i>A. nummularia</i>	1	1	0	0	4	-	5-45	present	0-present	root sample from isolated plant; seasonally variable
Plenchette and Duponnois, 2005	? Burkina Faso, Africa (only soil source given)	<i>A. nummularia</i>	0	0	1	1	10	-	77	present	0	individual plant; single host system; AMF colonisation increased with plant age
Püschel <i>et al.</i> , 2007a	Czech Republic	<i>A. sagittata</i> †	1	0	1	1	12	0-16	0-5	present	0	individual plant; annual host
Püschel <i>et al.</i> , 2007b	Czech Republic	<i>A. sagittata</i> †	1	0	1	1	28	0-41	0-25	-	0-7	individual plant; AMF colonisation increased with plant age
Straker <i>et al.</i> , 2007	North West, South Africa	<i>A. semibaccata</i>	0	1	0	1	36	-	26-72	29-63	0-2	whole plant excavated in the field
Aleman and Tiver, 2010	South Australia, Australia	<i>A. stipitata</i>	1	1	0	1	16	-	6	<1	<1	root sample from host in field plot
Cofré <i>et al.</i> , 2012	Córdoba, Salta and Jujuy, Argentina	<i>A. cordobensis</i>	1	1	0	0	18	-	0-99	<1-14	0	isolated whole plants excavated in the field; DSE detected
Soteras <i>et al.</i> , 2013	Córdoba, Argentina	<i>A. lampa</i>	1	1	0	0	25	-	4-82	present	0	soil core with roots at 5 depths
Becerra <i>et al.</i> 2014; Becerra <i>et al.</i> 2016	Córdoba, Argentina	<i>A. argentina</i>	1	1	0	0	25	-	4-50	present	0	soil core with roots at 5 depths
Zhao <i>et al.</i> 2017	Xinjiang, China	<i>A. tatarica</i>	1	1	0	1	?1	-	<1	present	0	whole plant root system; results unclear
Cardillo <i>et al.</i> 2018	Buenos Aires, Argentina	<i>A. semibaccata</i>	0	1	0	1	72	-	20-50	-	-	plot with roots extracted from soil core

Table 1. Published records of arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF) associated with *Atriplex* spp. (Amaranthaceae) (continued)

Source	Province/State/Region	Species	Natv	Fld	Inoc	\bar{x}	n	F%	M%	V%	A%	Observational units and other notes
Sidhoum and Fortas 2018	Oran, Algeria	<i>A. canescens</i>	0	1	1	1	12	-	23-40	-	<1-2	pot; varied with Cd treatment
		<i>A. halimus</i>	0	1	1	1	12	-	5-30	-	0-2	
de Melo <i>et al.</i> 2019	Pernambuco, Brazil	<i>A. nummularia</i>	0	0	1	1	40	-	8-10	present	0	individual plant
de Barros Silva Leite <i>et al.</i> 2020	Pernambuco, Brazil	<i>A. nummularia</i>	0	1	0	1	4	-	53-72	-	-	plot with roots extracted from soil sample
Jawneh and Riley, present study	Central Anatolia, Turkey	<i>A. amnicola</i>	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	individual plant in pot culture; putative DSE and Actinobacterium present
		<i>A. cinerea</i>	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	
		<i>A. nummularia</i>	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	

plants of each species showing stronger growth were harvested after 3 months (9 November 2020) and their roots were washed carefully to minimise breakage. Ten days before harvest the mean shoot lengths (mm) and branch numbers were recorded: *Atriplex amnicola*, 545 and 30; *A. cinerea*, 534 and 30; *A. nummularia* (Anu1), 464 and 20; and *A. nummularia* (Anu2), 401 and 18.

Root staining and assessment

Roots were cleared by boiling in 10% KOH for 3 min followed by rinsing several time in tap water. Cleared roots were boiled in a 5% royal blue ink (Pelikan 4001, Hanover, Germany) in white vinegar (5%) for 3 min and then destained in tap water acidified with few drops of vinegar for 20 min (Vierheilig *et al.*, 1998). Destained roots were kept in tap water at room temperature until examined microscopically on the same day. Stained roots were mounted on microscope slides and examined under a Leica DM 5500B light microscope (Wetzlar, Germany) for fungal hyphae, vesicles, arbuscules and other endophyte structures in root segments (c. 10 mm long).

Results

Table 1 summarises the data collated from the literature including entries for the present study (further details below). Across 28 reports, 25 *Atriplex* spp. have been studied, *A. argentina*, *A. atacamensis*, *A. canescens* (5), *A. confertifolia* (2), *A. coquimbensis*, *A. cordobensis*, *A. deserticola*, *A. gardneri* (3), *A. halimus* (2), *A. hortensis*[†], *A. julacea*, *A. lampa*, *A. madariagae*, *A. microphylla*, *A. mucronata*, *A. nummularia* (5), *A. patula*[†], *A. polycarpa*, *A. rosea*[†], *A. repanda*, *A. sagittata*[†] (2), *A. semibaccata* (2), *A. stipitata*, *A. tatarica* and *A. vesicaria* (2) ([†]annuals), mostly in a single investigation (except as indicated in parentheses for eight species). AMF were reported for all perennial species (except *A. polycarpa*) but not in all instances, and in only one of the annuals (viz. *A. sagittata*); however, the degree of colonisation was highly variable within and between studies (e.g., the differences in degree of colonisation in *A. nummularia* ranged from 1 to 40% within studies to over 70% between studies). Only one study reported colonisation frequency on a per plant basis with values up to 41%, however, when no colonisation was reported, the per plant frequency is given as zero (Table 1). Also, with overall colonisation and vesicular percentages ranging from 0% in many instances, it is clear that AMF were not present in all specimens of every species. (However, it should be noted that when data

are presented as means, this can mask the occurrence of uninfected specimens.) As expected, vesicular percentages were lower than overall colonisation percentages, but more notable was the low incidence of arbuscules. Arbuscules were reported for only nine species and at low percentages, except for *A. julacea* and *A. gardneri*, with up to 17 and 25% arbuscules, respectively, in separate studies conducted in the USA. As noted above, DSE were only reported for two studies, Barrow *et al.* (1997) and Cofré *et al.* (2012), in the USA and Argentina, respectively.

Overall, the studies found 22 *Atriplex* spp. with AMF association across five continents mostly in native species in field contexts (27 of 44 instances), but only nine with arbuscules. There was no obvious indication that the frequency or degree of AMF colonisation was related to locality or species endemicity, although the data are insufficient for hypothesis testing of these observations. The two species most commonly tested as exotics, *A. canescens* (US native) and *A. nummularia* (Australian native), both formed AMF associations in non-native contexts (soil and inoculum). After Miller *et al.* (1983) reported AMF associations in *A. confertifolia* occurred mostly in plants growing near other mycorrhizal species, assessments in subsequent studies were increasingly careful, focusing on isolated plants (or so deemed) in the field or single species pot experiments often with inoculation. AMF presence increased with age (e.g., Asghari *et al.*, 2005; Püschel *et al.*, 2007a) and depth (e.g., He *et al.*, 2002) when these factors were examined; with the depth effect, spores in soil were more common near the surface and arbuscules to depth, indicating occurrence of AMF in *Atriplex* can vary in response to range of factors (including community associations; Miller *et al.*, 1983).

Benefits of AMF associations in *Atriplex* was only demonstrated in a few studies. Williams *et al.* (1974) reported a tendency of AMF to improve growth in *A. canescens*, but the results were variable and indicative only. Asghari *et al.* (2005), and Plenchette and Duponnois (2005) report growth responses in *A. nummularia* (with and without detecting arbuscules, respectively) that might be considered more convincing. Consistent with these findings, de Melo *et al.* (2019) reported a positive correlation between degree of AMF colonisation and growth of *A. nummularia*, but there is a lack of clarity in this report, as there is likely to be confounding with other treatment effects and graphical presentation of this relationship is not given. Sidhoum and Fortas (2018) found AMF increased tolerance of *A. halimus* to heavy metal (Cd) contamination of soil. Therefore, despite 28

reports of AMF in *Atriplex*, clear evidence of functional benefits is limited.

When *A. amnicola*, *A. cinerea* and *A. nummularia* were grown as single plants in unfertilised, uninoculated field soil in the present study, none of the species formed AMF associations, with no vesicles or arbuscules found. Nevertheless, all plants grew well, and there was no evidence of any nutrient limitation despite being unfertilised and the soil having been collected from an unfertilised, long-fallowed field. Although no AMF colonisation was confirmed, endophytic fungal hyphae (some clearly septate) were present in the roots (Fig. 1C) with the proportion of positive root segments varying between species. *A. cinerea* had the most, with all root segments having colonisation, followed by *A. amnicola* with 86% positives. The two *A. nummularia* accessions were lower, having 33 and 40% positives. In all cases, this was associated with intracellular, elongated alignments (single or double rows) of microsclerotia (Fig. 1A, B) similar to those observed in other hosts (e.g., Venneman *et al.*, 2017; Fors *et al.*, 2020). Median microsclerotia number per mm of root in positive segments (each 10 mm) were >10 (range 1.5 to >10, n = 30) in *A. cinerea*, 3.7 (0.3 to >10, n = 26) in *A. amnicola*, and across both *A. nummularia* accessions 0.8 (0.1 to 6.7, n = 22). In addition to microsclerotia, all plants had darkly-stained endophyte development in the cortical cells (Fig. 1D) that was elongated with square ends appearing to have fully-colonised many infected cells. Closer microscope examination revealed these structures (densely-packed filaments with many small spore-like objects) were consistent with a species in the phylum Actinobacteria (Li *et al.*, 2016).

Discussion

The compilation in Table 1 shows that although only about 10% of *Atriplex* spp. have been investigated for AMF colonisation, AMF were reported in most instances. Of course, this could contain some bias, if some negative findings remain unreported. Perennials have received the most attention, as perennial *Atriplex* spp. are often viewed as important components of saline, semiarid-arid ecosystems. Therefore, annual *Atriplex* spp. clearly warrant greater attention. The consistent absence (apparent or real) or mostly low incidence of arbuscules is notable as this might be indicative of plant-fungus nutrient transfer in these slow-growing perennials in low-productive ecosystems occurring with minimal or no arbuscules (the latter as suggested by Plenchette and Duponnois, 2005). Alternatively, it could mean that these associations

Fig. 1. Representative examples of microsclerotia (A, B) and hyphae (C) in stained roots found in *Atriplex amnicola*, *A. cinerea* and *A. nummularia* after 3 months of growth in Niğde field soil in the greenhouse, and darkly-staining, elongated, intracellular colonisation (D) by an unidentified endophyte found in the three *Atriplex* spp. Scale bars c. 50 μ m

are not mutually beneficial in terms of interchange of nutrients, but are perhaps mutually beneficial in other ways (e.g., water relations and pathogen suppression; Sikes *et al.*, 2009). In some instances, the low incidence of arbuscules might be due to neighbouring plants being the primary AMF hosts and *Atriplex* an incidental host that does not readily become mycorrhizal on its own (e.g., Tester, 1993).

Also, *Atriplex* spp., in field contexts, might only have transient need for nutrient exchange, and regulate the timing and location of arbuscular development that makes its detection less likely (e.g., occurring at depth). However, the literature does not include examples of plants grown under controlled conditions (where more rapid plant growth and great nutrient demand could be

expected) with arbuscules present in particularly convincing numbers (Table 1). Therefore, the true nature and mutuality of AMF in *Atriplex* remains to be fully elucidated, and further research is justified, even if AMF in *Atriplex* are mostly determined by the AMF status of neighbouring plants (as suggested for *Quercus rubra*; Dickie *et al.*, 2001), because *Atriplex* will almost always occur as a member of a plant community, even when it is mostly annuals.

Although, DSE in *Atriplex* were reported in the earlier part of the history presented in Table 1 (Barrow *et al.*, 1997), these have been reported only once since (Cofré *et al.*, 2012). This might reflect a degree of confirmation bias, and some fungal infections interpreted as AMF might be misinterpretations of other fungi, or DSE were ignored because they were not the focus of an AMF study. However, there is growing awareness of that DSE are common and potentially function in beneficial ways for their plant hosts (Mandyam and Jumpponen, 2005). So, just as more work is needed on AMF in *Atriplex*, especially broadening this to include more annual species, DSE in *Atriplex* need greater research attention, if the broader microbial interactions of their root systems are to be understood.

The absence of AMF in the *Atriplex* plants grown in Niğde soil, in this simple preliminary investigation, is not particularly unexpected given chenopod species are most typically non-mycorrhizal. Nevertheless, *A. nummularia* is reported as having among the higher instances of colonisation in the genus and was positive in all five previous studies (Table 1). So *A. nummularia* is clearly a species capable of revealing the presence of *Atriplex*-infective AMF propagules in soil. With the status of *A. amnicola* and *A. cinerea* unknown, of course the expectation would be even lower, but still not dismissible given that AMF associations have been reported in nearly all *Atriplex* species examined. The reason for lack of colonisation of these three species could include: (1) lack of compatible propagules in the soil, (2) growth conditions not conducive, (4) insufficient growth period, (3) absence of mycorrhizal companion species, or (4) strong competition from other endophytes. Although the first is possible, it is unlikely because of the wide geographic occurrence of AMF with low host specificity (Yang *et al.* 2012), the fallow field from which the soil was sourced had supported a botanically-diverse range of annual and perennial pioneer plant (weed) species (including *Atriplex hastata*) for over 10 years or more, and four of the five AMF reports for *A. nummularia* were in non-native contexts (Table 1). The second is also not particularly likely. Niğde soil is alkaline, strongly P-fixing and low in Zn availability, and without added

fertiliser, and the strongly-growing *Atriplex* plants under glasshouse conditions would have largely exhausted the readily-available nutrients such that they would derive nutritional-benefit from forming AMF associations, if possible. With 3 months growth, AMF colonisation in *Atriplex* is possible (Tester, 1993), but most experimental studies (Table 1) assessed cultured plants after 4 to 6 months, so it is conceivable that the time was too short in this instance. The absence of suitable companion plant(s) (Tester *et al.*, 1987) seems a distinct possibility based on the work of Asghari *et al.* (2005) with low AMF in pots compared to *A. nummularia* from the field, but not from the work of Plenchette and Duponnois (2005) with 77% colonisation of *A. nummularia* in a single host system. Inter-endophyte competition, the last of these suggestions, is also a clear possibility (Fitter and Garbaye, 1994). However, research has tended to focus on AMF interactions with root pathogens or concomitant endophyte colonisation that enhances AMF colonisation, so information in support of this idea is limited. Vandegrift *et al.* (2015), based on co-inoculation studies in *Agrostis capillaris*, concluded that although endophytic mutualists are potentially competitors, plants have the ability to selectively direct carbon resources to provide optimal fitness benefit for itself and thereby control the relative proportions of competing mutualists (however, their conclusion is circumspect and they suggest that more integrative research is needed on symbiont consortia). Therefore, the latter two possibilities appear to be most deserving of further investigation, particularly inter-endophyte competition, as well as allowing more time for AMF associations to develop.

Of course, it is also possible that *Atriplex* spp. are in fact non-mycorrhizal and reports in the literature to the contrary have misinterpreted the observations made. Lambers and Teste (2013) would classify *Atriplex* (being in the Amaranthaceae) as non-mycorrhizal of what they term the Brassicaceae type, i.e., non-mycorrhizal plants that occupy habitats with high soil-P availability and limited interspecies competition. However, by way of example, *Atriplex* is species diverse in Australia and occurs widely across the majority of the continent (mostly below 20° S) (The Australasian Virtual Herbarium; avh.ala.org.au/occurrences/search?taxa=atriplex) particularly under alkaline, arid to semiarid conditions as well as in soils with moderate to high salinity, so its categorisation as being largely confined to non-P-limiting contexts seems problematic. Rather it seems more probable that many *Atriplex* spp. are weakly mycorrhizal and can form rudimentary AMF associations (as defined by Cosme *et al.* 2018) that

are transient in nature and highly variable (in time and space) in symptomology of colonisation. Likewise, AMF interactions with *Atriplex* might range from beneficial through to parasitic to a greater extent than in the more strongly arbuscular mycorrhizal plant species (Cosme *et al.* 2018). In which case, the lack of AMF colonisation of *Atriplex* in Niğde soil would fall within the expected range of responses for rudimentary arbuscular mycorrhizal species.

The presence of endophyte aggregations in the roots of *A. amnicola*, *A. cinerea* and *A. nummularia* (Fig. 1D; presumptively considered to be actinobacterial) appears to be a novel observation for the genus. *Atriplex cordobensis* has been reported to form nodules in response to colonisation by the nitrogen-fixing Actinobacteria, *Frankia* (Caucas and Oliva, 1990; Caucas and Abril, 1996), with that work being the only report of such a phenomenon. Free-living Actinobacteria can fix nitrogen (Sellstedt and Richau 2013), so in the evolutionary progression from free-living to nodule-inducing Actinobacteria symbiosis (Markmann and Parniske 2009), a non-nodulating endophytic associations must have occurred. The structures that facilitate nitrogen fixation in cultured *Frankia* (Torrey and Callahan, 1982) could equally be produced by *Frankia* as a non-nodulating endophyte. *Atriplex* in the Order Caryophyllales in the superastrids clade distinct from the superrosids that contain all known root-nodulating symbiotic plants (both actinorhizal and rhizobial) (Markmann and Parniske 2009). So the report of actinorhizal nodulation in *Atriplex* is anomalous (Caucas and Oliva, 1990; Caucas and Abril, 1996; field sampling of *A. nummularia* from several sites in South Australia failed to find evidence of nodulation; MH Ryder and ITR, unpublished observations), but many of genes that pre-empt nodulation and support mycorrhizal associations are likely to be present (Markmann and Parniske 2009). Therefore, the possibility that the structures observed in *A. amnicola*, *A. cinerea* and *A. nummularia* roots are actinobacterial and nutritionally-beneficial symbionts should be explored.

Conclusions

About 10% of *Atriplex* spp. have been investigated for AMF colonisation and this has been reported for 22 species. However, the low incidence of arbuscules creates some doubt about the functionality of these associations in nutrient transfer even though positive growth responses were reported in two studies. AMF associations were not confirmed for *A. amnicola*, *A. cinerea* and *A. nummularia* in a potentially conducive Central

Anatolian soil, further indicating the need for more work on AMF and other root endophytes in *Atriplex* across a wider range of conditions. However, DSE and a possible actinobacterial endophyte were found in these species, perhaps as competitors to AMF, likewise indicating the opportunity for further work on *Atriplex* considering a wider range of endophyte taxa, extending the work of Lucero *et al.* (2011) on seedborne endophytes to root endophytes in field contexts.

Acknowledgements

Assistance of Osameh Atiya with the photomicroscopy is gratefully acknowledged and Maarten Ryder for assistance with obtaining fruit of one accession of *A. nummularia*. The senior author is grateful for scholarships provided by Ayhan Şahenk Foundation and the Turkish Council of Higher Education. The encouragement of Prof. Andrew Smith to report this work is especially appreciated. Eniola Olowu kindly checked this report before release.

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Revision history

Ver. 001-01 - initial release

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